

Wild Asparagus in Olive Orchard

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Asparagus acutifolius

Asparagus acutifolius, belonging to the *Liliaceae* family, is a shrubby perennial species, spread around the Mediterranean basin. Since ever, due to its nutritional and nutraceutical properties, its spring sprout, the turion, has been hand-picked as a delicious, spontaneous product of *Mediterranean macchia*, hedgerows and wood margins, from the sea level up to hilly and low mountain elevations. Furthermore, the spontaneous bridled association between the olive tree and the wild asparagus is noteworthy. Such evidence arose the idea of domesticating the *A. acutifolius* in agroforestry systems within the olive groves. Several agronomic studies suggest this cultivation could significantly increase the poor profitability of the traditional olive plantations. The frugality of the species makes it a perfect candidate for cultivation of marginal Mediterranean lands. *A. acutifolius*, in fact, shows reduced requirements of water, light and nutrients and does not require pest control. Furthermore, with the exception of the spears, it is not grazed by most animals.

In practice, a farmer interested to the cultivation should verify the spontaneous presence of the species in or around his own grove: if present, no doubts about the place suitability. Then, the simplest scheme for a wild asparagus in grove plantation is on the tree lines, with 35 cm spacing between contiguous plants. Planting will be postponed to a shallow ploughing at 25 cm depth. The propagation material is a delicate aspect for this agroforestry system and its local value chain. Details are provided in an associated communication.

The harvest will start on the third year after the plantation. The productivity is in between 1 and 2 t ha⁻¹ per year. Given the high prices of the spears, the economic gain significantly overcomes that of the extra-virgin olive oil production, although the required work is substantially enhanced.

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